

Pharmacophore modeling using machine learning for screening Blood-Brain Barrier permeation of xenobiotics

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Abstract: Daily exposure to xenobiotics affects human health, especially the nervous system causing neurodegenerative diseases. The nervous system is protected by tight junctions present at the Blood-Brain barrier (BBB), but only molecules with desirable physicochemical properties can permeate. That's why permeation is a very decisive step in avoiding unwanted brain toxicity and also in developing neuronal drugs. In-silico methods are being implemented as an initial step to reduce the animal testing and time complexity of the in-vitro screening process. But, most in-silico methods are ligand-based, which considers only the physicochemical properties of ligands. However, the ligand-based methods have their own limitations and sometimes fail to predict the BBB permeation of xenobiotics. The objective of this work was to investigate the influence of pharmacophoric features of protein-ligand interaction on BBB permeation. For this, receptor-based pharmacophore and ligand-based pharmacophore fingerprints were developed using docking and Rdkit, respectively. Then, these fingerprints were trained on classical machine-learning models and compared with classical fingerprints. Among all, the ligand-based pharmacophore fingerprint achieved a slightly better (77% accuracy) comparison to the classical fingerprint method. In contrast, receptor-based pharmacophores did not lead to much improvement compared to classical descriptors. The performance can be further improved by considering efflux proteins like BCRP (Breast Cancer Resistance Protein) apart from P-gp (P-glycoprotein). However, limited data availability of other proteins for pharmacophoric interaction is a bottleneck to its improvement. Nonetheless, the developed models and exploratory analysis provided a path to extend the same framework for environmental chemicals, which are also xenobiotics like drugs. It can help in human health risk assessment by *a priori* screening for neurotoxicity-causing agents.

Keywords: Blood Brain Barrier; P-Glycoprotein; Neurotoxicity; Graph Neural Network; Machine Learning; Pharmacophore

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1. Introduction

Blood-Brain Barrier (BBB) is a dynamic physiological interface that controls the permeation of xenobiotics from blood to the central nervous system (CNS) [1,2]. This is essential to protect the brain from harmful chemicals, viruses, and bacteria, but at the same time, it becomes a hurdle for treating neurodegenerative diseases like schizophrenia, Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, etc. Often the drug developed for targeting CNS fails due to the low bioavailability because of the presence of BBB. The BBB mainly constitutes endothelial cells along with the mural cells, immune cells, glial cells, and astrocytes, creating a tight junction that prevents the passive diffusion of xenobiotics [1]. The BBB is also equipped with multiple protein complexes such as P-glycoprotein (P-gp), choline transporter, breast cancer resistance protein (BCRP), etc. which play a very crucial role in active transport [3].

The presence of efflux transporters serves to transfer the compound from the brain, thus acting as a hurdle in CNS drug permeation. P-gp is the most studied efflux transporter, which is responsible for drawing molecules back to blood circulation from CNS, thus, it prevents the therapeutic action of many drugs [4, 5]. Structurally P-gp consists of four domains, two of the hydrophobic transmembrane domains spans the lipid bilayer six times to make the channel-like structure that is responsible for substrate binding. The other two hydrophilic nucleotide-binding domains are present on the cytoplasmic face of the membrane, which regulates ATP metabolism for active transport [6]. Although mostly lipophilic molecules with smaller sizes (molecular weight <400 KDa) can cross BBB in significant amounts by passive diffusion, molecules having a higher molecular weight and hydrophilic in nature face difficulty for the same. As a consequence of this, from the enormously large space of chemicals, which is estimated to consist of 10^{60} compounds, only 2% of chemicals are being used to make CNS-specific drugs [6].

During the past decades, several rules and *in-silico* models were proposed based on the physicochemical properties of already marketed CNS drugs [7-9]. These *in-silico* models, up to certain extent help in the selection of ligands for CNS drug development. With recent algorithmic advancements, new methodologies based on graph theory were developed to incorporate the 2D and 3D features of the ligands [9]. Moving from this generalized classical ligand descriptors-based modeling, new methods which incorporate target receptors, such as pharmacophore modelling are being widely applied in computer-aided drug design.

Pharmacophore modelling has not been explored much in CNS screening, while in bioactive molecule screening, it has been used very often [5]. The pharmacophore model is based on the interaction between ligands and receptors. These interactions include all the information related to structural, spatial and chemical properties that are responsible for specific pharmacological actions. The interaction majorly involves non-covalent bonding like Hydrogen bonding, pi-pi stacking, ion-dipole interaction, etc. There are two types of pharmacophore modelling, one ligand-based and the other receptor-based, depending on the involvement of ligand and receptor during calculation [6]. Due to the high level of abstraction, pharmacophore features provide some advantages for building robust models [6]. Many commercial software are available such as ligandscout, Ludi, HS-pharm knowledge base, etc., for pharmacophore calculation and screening of ligands based on the desired receptor. But none of them are used for CNS ligand screening purposes.

In this work, we investigated the pharmacophoric modeling approach for screening the Blood-Brain Barrier Permeation of xenobiotics. The ligand-based and receptor-based pharmacophoric feature has been generated using a custom method. Generated fingerprints were tested on classical machine-learning algorithm models along with a common molecular fingerprint to compare their predictive power. To our best knowledge, the pharmacophoric aspect has never been addressed in the case of BBB permeation modeling. Implementation of different models also compares the performance of pharmacophore features with traditional descriptors/fingerprint methods for BBB classification.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Overall Methodological Concept

This study aims to investigate the effectiveness of different fingerprints generated based on pharmacophore modeling in deciphering the blood-brain barrier permeation of xenobiotics. With pharmacophore modeling, we try to incorporate the influence of the P-gp protein in the transportation process. To achieve this objective, our study is designed in the following steps (Fig.1):

- Collection of chemical data from reviewed literature sources and process through filtering and standardization process to get stabilized 3D structure. 96
- The scaffold of collected data is generated to analyze the distribution of the core structure of the chemical responsible for permeability. 97
- Stabilization and hydration of protein retrieved from the protein data bank (PDB) have been done for docking purposes. 98
- Three methods have been implemented to generate pharmacophore fingerprints; among them, two belong to the receptor-based and one to the ligand-based method. 99
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- a) Residue-based pharmacophore is generated by docking the P-gp substrates and extracting the most-common residues involved in the interaction. The residues are then mapped with the interaction of the drug molecule to generate a 62-bit fingerprint (Fig. 2). 105
- b) Interaction-type pharmacophore is generated using the docked drug data, which is further processed with the proLIF library to generate a 9-bit fingerprint (Fig. 3). 106
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- Generated fingerprint and classical fingerprint were then trained on a classical algorithm such as Support Vector Machine (SVM), RF (Random Forest), and naïve Bayes for comparison. A newly developed graph model is also implemented for comparison. 115
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Figure 1. Methodological Framework for Pharmacophore Generation. Firstly, the protein is passed through a pre-processing phase which includes energy minimization, protonation and distribution of charges. Along with this, drugs and p-gp substrates are standardized and finally passed through the energy minimization process to get a stable 3D structure. Using this pre-processed data, three types of fingerprints are generated. 1a. Residue-based fingerprint: P-gp substrates are docked and interacting amino acids are extracted, and simultaneously docked drug interaction residues are mapped over it to generate a 120
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fingerprint. 1b. Interaction-type fingerprint: Drug molecules are docked, and then docked data are processed with the ProLIF library 2. Ligand-based Fingerprint: Drug data along with its 3D coordinates are processed in Rdkit.

2.2. Data Collection and Scaffold Generation

A wide fraction of data for the present work was reviewed from multiple sources [7–10]. We found that the recent paper from *Fanwang et.al* contains all the data from our reviewed sources, so this database was considered for our study. The dataset comprised 7807 molecules in SMILES (Simplified Molecular Input Line Entry System) [11] notation with 4956 molecules as BBB+ and 2851 molecules as BBB-. The dataset is curated from more than 50 peer-reviewed literature, which leads to the heterogeneous endpoint of molecules. Some of the endpoints are encoded as a binary value, with 1 depicting as permeable and 0 representing non-permeable. While in others, permeability is represented as a continuous logBB value (concentration in brain/concentration in blood). Various threshold values for logBB have been defined to include or exclude molecules in either of the categories. The threshold value is discussed in the respective database paper [10]. For filtering duplicate molecules, an extended connectivity fingerprint (ECFP4) [12] of compounds was generated and using this fingerprint, Tanimoto's score was calculated. Based on the Tanimoto score, similar molecules were grouped, and a single element from each group was selected upon manual inspection. After filtering processes, the data size was reduced to 3337 molecules. It was observed that most of the duplicate molecules are stereoisomers, and these stereoisomers are explicitly added to the database, as mentioned by the author. The stereochemistry of molecules is very crucial for defining the various properties of molecules, as well as interactions with the receptors, but in this work, stereoisomers are neglected to reduce excessive computational cost. Filtered molecules were standardized by stripping salt, neutralizing molecules, and converting SMILES into the canonical form using the Molecule Validation and Standardization (MolVS) library [14]. Also, single atoms molecules like Kr, Ne, C, Li, O, Ar, Xe, etc., which don't add anything to the organic drug domain, were removed from the database. Additionally, molecules whose 3D structures cannot be generated and optimized in 5000 steps through the steepest descent algorithm using MMFF94 forcefield [15] were neglected. Optimization of molecules has been done using Open Babel's [16] command-line tools. The final library of 3019 molecules in SDF (structure-data file) format was curated with 1197 molecules as BBB+ and 1822 as BBB-. A filtered and optimized molecular database is publicly available on github.

In addition, 358 P-gp substrates (encoded in SMILES notation) were curated from Drug Bank [17]. These molecules help in the generation of amino acid residues mapping of the active site (Fig. 2). This residue map helps to generate a receptor-based pharmacophore fingerprint (further discussion in section 2.5.1 method DockedFP 1a)). During the pre-processing of P-gp substrates, 57 molecules failed in the 3D geometry optimization. The remaining structures were stored as an SDF library for docking. The p-gp dataset is publicly available on github.

For scaffold analysis of drug molecules, we used SMILES of molecules to generate the Murcko Scaffold framework [18] of each drug molecule using the Rdkit. Murcko scaffold is a graph-based structure enumeration method; it dissects the cyclic molecule into four units, i.e., rings, framework, linker, and side chains. The generated scaffold was grouped based on its structural similarity. BBB permeability probability for the scaffold was calculated for analysis. For concise and interpretive visualization of high-dimensional drug space, the TMAP [19] algorithm developed by Raymond's lab has been used. TMAP visualization file and its code is available in the github repository.

2.3. P-gp receptor preparation

The protein model of P-gp is retrieved from Protein Data Bank [20] with ID 6fn1. The structural resolution of protein is 3.58 Å. The stereochemical validation to investigate the $\phi - \psi$ dihedral angle in the Ramachandran plot is done on a new version of PROCHECK software (European Bioinformatics Institute, Cambridge, UK) [21]. The Ramachandran plot statistics showed 88.1% (1270) and 11.6% (167) residues in the most favored regions and allowed regions, respectively (Fig. S1). While the expected value for comparison of the structure having 2 Å of resolution is more than 90% in the most favored region. Docking preparation is initiated by energy minimization of protein using ModRefiner [22], which helps to achieve the lowest energy conformation of a molecule. Energy minimized structure has a TM (Template modeling)-score of 0.9946 as compared to the initial structure, which depicts that there is almost no loss in fold during energy minimization. A python script “prepare_receptor.py” of AutoDock Tools [23] has been used to protonate and redistribute Kollman partial charges over the stabilized protein. Finally, the protein has been converted to the ready-to-dock format of AutoDock Vina [24] i.e., pdbqt (Protein Data Bank, Partial Charge, and Atom Type). Although, it is well known that P-gp has multiple binding sites such as H-site (binding Hoechst 33482), R-site (Binding rhodamine 123), and P-site (Binding prazosin and progesterone), etc. [25], however, there is no database of P-gp substrates with the specific binding site available till now. Hence, we considered the previous work on structural and functional aspects of P-gp, which mentioned that majorly transmembrane helices from 4-6 and 10-12 are involved in substrate Binding [26, 27]. So, the center coordinates (X=160 Å, Y=145.4 Å, Z= 142.88 Å) with a grid box size of 40 Å between these transmembrane helices were considered.

2.4. Ligand preparation

Optimized ligands SDF library was processed using a python script “mk_prepare_ligand.py” of the Meeko library [28]. Meeko is a python-based library for the preparation of small molecules for docking, developed by Forli lab at the Center of Computational Structural Biology (CCSB) at Scripps Research. This script carries out all the necessary pre-processing such as the distribution of charges (Gasteiger charges), the addition of polar hydrogen atoms, and finally, the conversion from PDB to PDBQT format.

Once the raw material required for docking was assembled, then two types of pharmacophore fingerprints were developed, i.e., ligand-based and receptor-based (Residue based and Interaction-type based). For ligand-based pre-developed method from Rdkit was implemented, while AutoDock Vina and Python were used to generate custom structure-based interaction fingerprint.

2.5. Interaction fingerprint generation

2.5.1. Receptor-Based

Method DockedFP(1a): Residue-Based

High throughput docking of the Drug bank’s P-gp substrate to the binding site of P-gp was done using python (ver.3.7) [29]; under the hood, it implements the Autodock-vina [24] command in a parallel fashion (Fig. 2). While docking, 31 molecules were neglected due to an error in atom-type notation. Properly docked ligands were then processed through the “process_VinaResult.py” script of the AutoDock tools repository to extract the list of residues responsible for binding with the drug molecule. 62 most common residues of active binding sites have been extracted. A plot of the most common residues is present in the supplementary file (Fig. S2). For mapping, a python dictionary of these 62 residues was built. The optimized SDF library of the drugs was then processed through the ligand preparation stage and then docked at the narrow channel of the P-gp receptor. Interacting residues were then extracted and looped through the mapping dictionary to generate a 62-bit vector array where 1 and 0 represent the presence and absence of interaction.

Figure 2. Residue-based pharmacophore Fingerprint: **DockedFP(1a)**. 1) P-gp substrate is docked with the receptor. 2) Active site residue interacting with P-gp substrates is mapped. 3) Drug is docked with the P-gp receptor. 4) Residues of active site binding to drug is mapped. 5) Custom python loop to generate interaction fingerprint using both P-gp substrate and drug mappings.

Method DockedFP(1b): Interaction-Type Based

Interaction type fingerprint generation implements the 9-bit array containing only bonding type information such as cationic, anionic, hydrophobic, hydrogen, etc. ProLIF library [30] was used to encode interaction type information as a fingerprint (Fig. 3). ProLIF is a python-based library developed by the Chemosim-lab; it is used to generate interaction fingerprints for complexes like ligands, protein, DNA, or RNA based on the data extracted from molecular dynamics, docking simulations, and experimental structures. Docked PDBQT files were processed through the “mk_copy_coords.py” script of the meeko library for SDF conversion. SDF files, along with receptor protein, were then fed with the default threshold distance for each interaction. Finally, the library generates the interaction-type array as a bit vector with 0 and 1 depicting absence and presence.

Figure 3. Interaction-type pharmacophore fingerprint: **DockedFP(1b)**. 1) Standardized and stabilized drug molecules are docked with the P-gp receptor. 2) Docked drug data and P-gp receptor is

imputed in the ProLIF library. 3) Data is processed using the distance boundaries given for different interaction types and finally 9-bit fingerprint is generated.

2.5.2. Ligand-Based

Method 2: Rdkit Pharmacophore Fingerprint

In ligand-based pharmacophore generation, the structure of the receptor was not taken into consideration [6]. It solely relies on the features of ligands that contribute to the interaction with receptors. Ligand-based pharmacophore generated by Rdkit leads to 39971 long-bit array fingerprints. Generated fingerprints consist of features such as hydrophobicity, donor capacity, affinity, acidic group, basic group, aromatic attachment, etc. As compared to ECFP4 fingerprint generation, this fingerprint is much more memory intensive, but it includes all the properties of a molecule, just like the ECFP4 fingerprint. The size of the fingerprint can be reduced using the PCA (Principle Component Analysis) and newly developed deep learning method like Auto-encoders, which takes high-dimensional feature size as input and return low-dimensional representation while preserving the information and semantics.

2.6. GNN Implementation

Two variants of graph neural network (GNN) that is, graph convolution network (GCN) and graph attention network (GAT) have been trained for 200 epochs at a batch size of 256 with the Adam optimizer at a learning rate of 0.001. The optimal configuration (Fig.4) of GCN consists of two feature extractor layers embedded with a residual block, followed by a non-linear transformation block in each. The extractor layer was followed by a non-linearly transformed predictor layer with a sigmoid as an activation layer for output. While the GAT network is a combination of two multi-headed Graph attention layers as feature extractors with elu (exponential linear unit) activation, and the predictor layer is the same as GCN. Hyperparameters of both networks were tabulated in Supplementary Table S1. For building neural networks, blocks of graph operation layers from the PyTorch geometric library have been compiled into the whole graph neural network architecture using PyTorch [31]. DeepChem library was used to populate the node features vector of the molecular graph. Fundamental features of molecules were atom type, formal charge, hybridization, hydrogen bonding, aromaticity, degree/connectivity, number of hydrogens, and partial charge, were encoded in a one-hot feature vector to make it easy for algorithms to find the local minima during learning.

Figure 4. The architecture of Graph neural network models. GCN and GAT networks almost share the same architecture, and the main difference is in their Block layer, i.e., GCN block performs the convolution to learn the low-level representation of the molecular graph, while GAT implements multi-headed attention with convolution to learn the weighted representation of the molecular graph. GCN network uses ReLU (Rectified linear

activation unit) as an activation function while GAT implements elu (Exponential linear unit) between the layer stacking. Finally, for the downstream task, both implement the same architecture of the predictor layer. The dashed line represents the internal architecture of each block in the network.

2.7. Model Validation

After ensuring a clean and representative compilation of the dataset, three algorithms were trained using different representations of pharmacophore interaction and molecular features alone or combinations of it. For training and experimental measurement across a variety of drug discovery projects, machine learning models such as support vector machine (SVM) [32], a tree-based model like random forest (RF) [33], and Bayesian statistics were used [6]. To ensure the robustness of the predictive results, all classical machine learning models were trained and evaluated through an exhaustive 5-fold stratified cross-validation method. This means the whole dataset was divided into 5 subsets with equally distributed classes, and 4 sets among them were used for training while the remaining one was for validation. The classical algorithms were implemented using the popular python scikit-learn [34] machine learning package. A comparison of the performance of these models with newly emerged GNN variants was done.

2.8. Evaluation Metrics

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{\text{Total samples}} \quad \text{eq. 1}$$

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{Number of TP}}{TP + FP} \quad \text{eq. 2}$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{Number of TP}}{TP + FN} \quad \text{eq. 3}$$

$$F1 \text{ score} = 2 * \frac{\text{Precision} * \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad \text{eq. 4}$$

$$MCC = \frac{TP \times TN - FP \times FN}{\dots} \quad \text{eq. 5}$$

Note: TP (True Positive), TN (True Negative), FP (False Positive), FN (False Negative), MCC (Matthews correlation coefficient)

To evaluate the results of the model, several common classification metrics as mentioned in eq. 1-5 and AUC-ROC score were calculated using the scikit-learn package. The most common metric used for model evaluation is accuracy (eq. 1), but this statistic is not suitable for unbalanced data sets. Precision measures what proportion of BBB+ classes are actually positive (eq. 2). Other metrics, such as recall/sensitivity (eq 3.) will assess the model's ability to predict actual BBB+ molecules as positive. It is mainly dedicated to assessing false-negative classes. The harmonic mean of precision and recall gives an F1 score that helps in comparing different classifiers (eq. 4). Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC) is used to measure the quality of binary classification and multiclass classification (eq. 5). It also handles unbalanced classes. Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristics (AUROC) score measures the performance of the classification model. ROC represents the probability curve, while AUC represents the degree and measure of separability.

Processing of molecules for optimization, validation, and docking was done on a Dell server with two 8 cores of Xenon processors running at 3.29 GHz, with 128 GB of RAM. For classical and Graph-based machine learning 16 GB, NVIDIA RTX A4000 GPU has also been leveraged.

3. Results

3.1. Scaffold-based Chemical Space Analysis

For the first-time structural diversity analysis of the drugs was done to determine *a priori* whether a compound's backbone/scaffold is suitable for crossing the barrier or not. During scaffold analysis, we found that in the chemical space of 3337 molecules, for 196 molecules, no scaffold was generated as they were acyclic, while the remaining 1864 were cyclic molecules. 79.2% of scaffold clusters generated from cyclic compounds consist of only one unique molecule. While in the remaining scaffolds, molecule distribution ranges from 2- 200 molecules in the scaffold group as shown in Fig S3. As expected, benzene was found to be the most common scaffold, which suggests that molecules possessing rigid structures can be used as a good base for optimizing lead candidates [18]. Further, to assess the permeability power of each scaffold, the permeable probability of each scaffold was calculated. Scaffolds having a probability above 0.6 were assigned permeable scaffolds while below 0.4 as non-permeable (Fig. 4). Scaffolds having a probability between 0.4 and 0.6 were considered neutral. The probability score of some top scaffolds is mentioned in Table S2. This categorization provided a broad picture of classifying a molecule's permeability on the basis of scaffold which can be helpful to narrow down the ligand space. In addition, a molecular framework having a high probability may be considered as a starting point for *de novo* BBB permeable drug development, whose therapeutic nature can be further tuned by adding favorable substituents by a medicinal chemist. Other parameters such as polar surface area, molecular weight, lipophilicity, flexibility, and hydrogen bond donors have been consistently identified as crucial properties for tweaking BBB permeability for drug design [35]. We found that addition or deletion in functional groups over the scaffold base may lead to changes in the above-mentioned parameters, which eventually leads to an increase or decrease in permeability. This phenomenon was visualized using TMAP, showing the arrangement of each drug molecule around its common denominator scaffolds and the change in the permeability with slight modification in substituents. For example, the incorporation of substituents fluorine in scaffolds enhanced the lipophilicity of molecules and reduced the efflux ratio [35]. Some most common permeable scaffolds excluding benzene have structures/substructures very similar to Gona-1,3,5(10)-trien-3-ol, Diphenylmethane, Benzodiazepine, Cyclopropyl benzene, 2,4,6-Pyrimidinetrione, etc. possessing rigid system (Fig S2). It may be possible that these common permeable scaffolds have low TPSA, suggesting that TPSA can be used as a parameter for differentiating between CNS and non-CNS drugs [33]. But, in our analysis, we did not find major differences in TPSA distribution between permeable and non-permeable, which requires further investigation to reach a conclusion (Fig. S4-S6). Apart from TPSA, other defining properties, such as hydrogen bond donor (HBD) and hydrogen bond acceptor (HBA), may also attribute to the permeability (Fig. S4-S6); but it depends on the functional group substituted over the scaffold. In this work, we did not choose multiple parameters for analysis, but there lies a scope to investigate it further. In short, scaffold analysis can be considered the first step in the virtual screening of drugs.

Figure 5. Grouping scaffold based on BBB permeability probability. Scaffolds having permeability probability above 0.6 and below 0.6 are assigned as permeable and non-permeable scaffolds. Scaffolds between 0.4 and 0.6 are grouped as neutral.

3.2 Classical ML models

Four different algorithms based on classical learning have been implemented to build predictive models using chemical fingerprints, pharmacophoric features, or a combination of both (Table 1). Receptor-based generated pharmacophore fingerprints were first tested on a dummy model, which randomly selects class labels from the uniform distribution of data points. The dummy model gives 50% accuracy for methods DockedFP (1a) and DockedFP (1b) generated fingerprints. It was considered as a baseline to validate whether the generated fingerprints hold any relevant information or not. Other models trained using DockedFP (1a) and DockedFP (1b) performed better than the baseline model with 60–63% of accuracy and 69–74% of F1 score but less than in comparison to ECFP4 fingerprint, which showed 72–76% accuracy and 78–81% of F1 score. This might be because the size of the ECFP4 fingerprint is 1024 bits long; hence it contains more elaborate information about the topological properties, substructure information, and common molecular features like stereochemical information, which is essential to define the biological endpoint of the molecule just like QSAR models [12,13]. In contrast, pharmacophore fingerprints of method DockedFP (1a) and method DockedFP (1b) have 62 and 8-bit vector sizes, which contain limited information only about the binding site residues and the type of interaction. Further, the ECFP4 fingerprint was merged with both structure-based generated fingerprints to mitigate this lack of information. Upon combination, the performance of the combinational fingerprint is similar (72–76% of accuracy) to the ECFP4 fingerprint, which shows that the addition of pharmacophoric features to the structural fingerprint does not enhance the predictive power. It could be due to the dominance of ligand-based molecular fingerprints over pharmacophoric features developed by custom methods. Because the algorithms trained solely on structural pharmacophoric have significant predictive power (61–63%), but when merged with higher order size fingerprint, it is considered noise and gets neglected by the algorithm. We also tried adding continuous descriptors (Molecular weight, Partition coefficient (Log P), Topological Polar Surface Area) with pharmacophoric features, but this resulted in a decline in model performance (result not shown). This decline in performance with the addition of descriptors because of their continuous values and the combination of the continuous and binary values may confuse the algorithms to learn the relevant pattern and may reduce the performance of the model. That's why the addition of the ECFP4 fingerprint is preferred over descriptors. The combined model (ECFP4+ DockedFP (1a & 1b)) gave 76% accuracy on SVM and RF algorithm, while the performance dropped to 72% on Naïve Bayes. Ligand-based pharmacophore generated using Rdkit performs slightly better than the ECFP4 fingerprint with the Random

Forest algorithms (77% accuracy) because ligand-based pharmacophore facilitates the understanding of structural and activity relationship with the target receptor. The ligand-based pharmacophore also achieves the highest precision (78% on RF) among them, which shows a decrease in false prediction. This satisfies our hypothesis that some molecules have the physicochemical property in the desirable range for permeation but still it's not able to permeate because of the involvement of P-gp. By adding ligand interaction in the fingerprint, the model manages to capture this information up to a certain extent. There is a decrease in ligand-based pharmacophore performance with SVM (75%) and Naïve Bayes (71%) algorithm. Among the three algorithms, the better performance of the Random forest is attributed to its tree-like distribution of feature points and the implicit "ensemble learning" which enables multiple decision tree models to train on the same data [36]. Also, binary fingerprints complement the features of the random forest as they make it easier for the algorithm to split nodes based on "yes" and "no" until a leaf node is reached. Random forest algorithms are highly prone to overfitting as well, so the mindful tuning of hyperparameters is required for their better performance.

The performance of the structure-based generated pharmacophore is lower than the ligand-based pharmacophore for BBB permeation modelling. These might be the reasons for this.

i) The BBB has multiple efflux transporter, but we considered only P-gp due to limited data.

ii) For pharmacophore generation specific binding site on a protein is crucial, but P-gp has a broad substrate binding site. In this case, a common site is assumed for the binding of all drug molecules [37].

These assumptions were taken to make the model simplistic which might be the reason for the decline in the performance of the pharmacophore model. Otherwise, pharmacophore-based modeling is the heart of computer-aided drug design (CADD) modeling [6]. It helps to prioritize the promising derivatives from a wide chemical space. Pharmacophore models are often used in virtual screening because they cover different important aspects that are important for the activity of the compound. Commercial tools for pharmacophore-based modeling account for the presence of important physicochemical properties for biological activity and molecular docking to calculate the fitting of the compound [5]. Having both fitting and physicochemical data, the success rate of virtual screening exceeds. Pharmacophore modeling for BBB permeation is a challenging task as the permeation process is controlled by multiple parameters and interactions; modeling all the interactions simultaneously is challenging due to limited data availability.

3.4. Comparison with GNN models

The application of deep learning in the field of chemicals/drug discovery has been very prevalent in the form of GNN because of the resemblance of the molecular structure to a graph[36]. We found that both convolution and attention networks provided similar results for accuracy (74%), precision (77%), f1 score (79%) whereas recall value was higher with convolution (80%) than with attention (78%) (Table 1). Additional metrics such as Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC) and AUC-ROC score has given better result for convolution with attention (51% of MCC and 75% of AUC-ROC) than alone with convolution (47% of MCC and 72% AUC-ROC). Tweaking in the input features of the graph model, such as the addition of interaction-type information from pharmacophore data, might help to elevate the performance. Training of the graph network has been monitored by overfitting sensitive metric "loss value" to choose the training epoch and learning rate. The new variant of GCN named relational graph convolution networks (RGCN) sounds promising for future work with multiple pharmacophores [39]. It can be explored further in the continuation of this work. If GNN leads to improvement in prediction, it can help

in screening new biological entities for CNS targeting and exclude molecules that are toxic to CNS.

Table 1. Comparison of models on the different fingerprint.

Models	Features	Accuracy (Train/Test)	Precision (Train/Test)	Recall (Train/Test)	F1 score (Train/Test)
Baseline	DockedFP (1a)	0.50/0.50	0.60/0.61	0.48/0.49	0.53/0.54
	DockedFP (1b)	0.50/0.50	0.61/0.61	0.49/0.49	0.55/0.55
SVM	ECFP4 fingerprint	0.92/0.76	0.91/0.77	0.96/0.86	0.94/0.82
	DockedFP (1a)	0.62/0.61	0.62/0.62	0.93/0.92	0.75/0.74
	DockedFP (1b)	0.71/0.63	0.70/0.64	0.93/0.87	0.80/0.74
	Rdkit Pharmacoprint	0.88/0.75	0.84/0.75	0.98/0.89	0.90/0.81
	ECFP4+ DockedFP (1a)	0.92/0.76	0.91/0.77	0.96/0.87	0.93/0.82
	ECFP4+ DockedFP (1b)	0.93/0.76	0.92/0.77	0.97/0.86	0.94/0.81
Random Forest	ECFP4 fingerprint	1/0.76	1/0.76	1/0.86	1/0.81
	DockedFP (1a)	0.62/0.61	0.62/0.62	0.92/0.91	0.75/0.74
	DockedFP (1b)	0.91/0.60	0.90/0.64	0.95/0.73	0.92/0.69
	Rdkit Pharmacoprint	0.99/0.77	0.99/0.78	0.99/0.84	0.99/0.81
	ECFP4+DockedFP (1a)	1/0.76	1/0.76	1/0.87	1/0.81
	ECFP4+DockedFP (1b)	1/0.76	1/0.76	1/0.87	1/0.81
Naïve Byes	ECFP4 fingerprint	0.76/0.72	0.78/0.75	0.83/0.80	0.81/0.78
	DockedFP (1a)	0.62/0.62	0.62/0.62	0.9/0.9	0.74/0.74
	DockedFP (1b)	0.61/0.60	0.66/0.64	0.75/0.74	0.70/0.69
	Rdkit Pharmacoprint	0.72/0.71	0.72/0.71	0.90/0.89	0.80/0.79
	ECFP4+DockedFP (1a)	0.76/72	0.78/0.75	0.84/0.8	0.81/0.77
	ECFP4+ DockedFP (1b)	0.76/72	0.78/0.75	0.84/0.81	0.81/0.78
Graph Convolution Network (GCN)	Descriptors	0.81/0.74	0.83/0.77	0.85/0.80	0.84/0.79
Graph Attention Network (GAT)	Descriptors	0.83/0.74	0.87/0.77	0.84/0.78	0.85/79

*Note: Additional metrics such as Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC) and AUC-ROC score have been tabulated in supplementary as Table S2:

4. Conclusions

This study tries to investigate whether the addition of the pharmacophoric interaction in the screening process for CNS-targeted can elevate the robustness of the predictive models. To perform this analysis, chemical data has been curated from different sources and thoroughly filtered to remove redundant molecules. Also, the data was passed through a computationally expensive process to generate an optimized 3D structures library of the molecules and P-gp substrates. This SDF molecules library is made publicly available for future exploration. The generated data were processed through various methods to create interaction fingerprints. The generated interaction fingerprints and combinations of docked and ECFP4 fingerprints were trained on classical machine learning algorithms. It is concluded that ligand-based pharmacophore performs better than traditional ECFP4 fingerprint in classifying permeable and non-permeable classes. In contrast, receptor-based pharmacophore modeling is still not mature enough for the CNS screening process. We used the custom method to generate pharmacophore fingerprints, while using the commercial tool might help to elevate the predictive performance. From this work

foundation of pharmacophore modeling using machine learning for CNS screening has been laid out. Its performance can be further improved in future work by the application of the relational graph convolutional network, which can involve multiple pharmacophores generated from interaction with different proteins and also the physicochemical properties of drugs at once in modeling.

We tried to move one step ahead from the traditional descriptor-based screening method to protein-drug interaction for evaluating BBB permeability. Till now, *in-silico* models are focused on passive diffusion as a mechanism of drug permeation across the BBB which may not be true. We tried to incorporate protein-ligand interaction using single efflux transporter, but multiple transporters can contribute to the permeation mechanism [23]. In the future multi, pharmacophore modeling can be implemented to improve the predictive capability. Currently, the data available regarding active transport through BBB is limited, which restricts our potential to develop a robust *in-silico* model. Even though P-gp is the most studied protein in the domain of efflux transporter, still the database of P-gp substrate with the specific binding site is not available. Recent advancements in technology and high throughput screening techniques for the *in-vitro* and *in-vivo* models will populate data that can be used in the future to make an efficient and reliable model. Nonetheless, this model serves as laying the ground for considering active transport along with passive diffusion for BBB permeation. Proposed Framework can also support the 3Rs principle and the use of such methods within read-across approaches [40] or in a wider integrative translational framework for chemical induced neurotoxicity [41]. The current modeling pipeline is a generic framework that can be applied in the field of human risk assessment, as *in-silico* method for screening neurotoxic environmental chemicals has not been implemented so far. Screened neurotoxic chemicals can then be further narrowed down by studying their kinetic properties and active concentration in CNS using dynamic modelling such as PBPK (Physiology Based Pharmacokinetics) [40,41]. This integrative approach of QSAR (Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship) and PBPK will ease the load of *in-vitro* experiments and will also be helpful in revealing the adverse effects of these toxicants on different organs/system such as liver, gut, and immune system in mechanistic way [2,42].

Github:

<https://github.com/Crispae/Pharmacophore-modeling-using-machine-learning-for-screening-Blood-Brain-Barrier-permeation-of-xenobi>

Supplementary Materials: The following are available online at www.mdpi.com/xxx/s1, Figure S1: title, Table S1: title, Video S1: title.

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Abbreviations

BBB	Blood-Brain Barrier
BCRP	Breast cancer resistance protein
P-gp	P-glycoprotein
CNS	Central Nervous system
SMILES	Simplified Molecular Input Line Entry System
ECFP4	Extended Connectivity Fingerprint
MMFF94	Merck Molecular Force Field
SDF	Structure-Data File
TMAP	Tree MAP
PDB	Protein Data Bank
PDBQT	Protein Data Bank, Partial Charge and Atom Type
GNN	Graph Neural Network
GCN	Graph Convolution Network
GAT	Graph Attention Network
ELU	Exponential Linear Unit
SVM	Support Vector Machine
RF	Random Forest
TPSA	Topological Polar Surface Area
HBA	Hydrogen Bond Acceptor
HBD	Hydrogen Bond Donor
RGCN	Relational Graph Convolution Network

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